

D6.1

EXPLOITATION

PLAN V1

DELIVERABLE D6.1

WP6, T6.1

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TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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ACRONYMS

CSLs	Citizen Science Labs
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
TG(s)	Target Group(s)
TRL/SRL	Technology/Societal Readiness Level
TTM	Time to market
USP	Unique Selling Proposition

1 INTRODUCTION

This document presents the preliminary version of the SPOON exploitation plan (Deliverable D6.1), developed within the framework of WP6 “Exploitation, replication and policy uptake”. Its main purpose is to provide a first structured view of the SPOON Key Exploitable Results (KERs), the partners involved in their development, and the initial strategic directions for their uptake, replication, and long-term sustainability. The plan is designed to evolve iteratively, supporting the continuous exploitation readiness of project outcomes throughout the entire project lifecycle.

The exploitation strategy in SPOON is intrinsically connected with the project’s mission to empower citizens and communities in driving healthier and more sustainable food behaviours. As such, the outputs generated by the project are not only expected to generate academic knowledge or technical tools, but to be actively used by public authorities, civil society organisations, professionals along the value chain and citizen groups across Europe. This deliverable therefore marks a first milestone in structuring the routes and conditions for those outputs to reach their intended audiences and be adopted beyond the project's duration.

This first version of the exploitation plan builds on the preliminary mapping of SPOON's exploitable results and stakeholder needs, as defined in the proposal and further refined in the first months of the project through internal support to all partners on identifying their project outputs. The next iteration of the plan (D6.2) will include refined characterisations of each KER, initial business modelling efforts where relevant, and targeted engagement with early adopters.

1.1 DELIVERABLE OVERVIEW

Deliverable D6.1 provides the initial framework for the exploitation strategy of the SPOON project. It introduces the twelve preliminary KERs identified by the consortium, spanning a variety of outputs: GDPR-compliant digital tools (e.g. personal data wallet, DataU platform), behavioural science-based interventions, replication and capacity-building assets (e.g. SPOON Academy), and policy instruments such as the recommendation package and monitoring toolkit. While their detailed characterisation will take place progressively throughout the project, this deliverable lays the groundwork for their assessment, validation, and uptake planning.

The document begins with a structured mapping of the KERs and presents a categorisation of Target Groups (TGs), grouped into four areas: Enablers and Implementers, System Shapers, Knowledge Multipliers, and Citizen Co-Creators. Each group’s needs and value relationship to the KERs are examined, forming the basis for audience-tailored exploitation strategies. This is complemented by an analysis of opportunities for collaboration with EU-funded projects under initiatives such as FOOD2030, supported using PNO’s [WheesBee tool](#) and active engagement of all partners.

A forward-looking trends analysis identifies four macro-level developments shaping the exploitation potential of SPOON: (1) citizen data sovereignty, (2) behavioural insights in public policy, (3) EU data governance frameworks, and (4) sustainability education. Their implications, both opportunities and constraints, are discussed in relation to the project's KERs and stakeholder engagement strategies.

Finally, the deliverable introduces SPOON's internal exploitation methodology. This includes the use of a dedicated KER master file, a maturity assessment approach adapted from the European Commission's Innovation Radar, and an IPR tracking structure grounded in the Consortium Agreement. These tools and processes will be used iteratively in the next phases (D6.2 and D6.3), to progressively develop robust, partner-owned exploitation plans that align with stakeholder needs and maximise long-term impact.

2.1 MAPPING SPOON'S OUTPUTS

The identification of SPOON's KERs builds upon the project's structure and logic, particularly the co-creation processes activated within the Citizen Science Labs (CSLs) and the development of enabling tools and policy recommendations. The KERs are understood not only as technical or digital outputs given the nature of the project, but also as methodologies, capacity-building assets, policy frameworks, and community-based innovations that can generate impact during and beyond the project's lifetime.

At this stage (M6), a preliminary list of twelve KERs has been identified in alignment with the Grant Agreement and two online interactions with all beneficiaries. These include, among others, the SPOON toolset (a set of digital services for data governance and behaviour change), the SPOON Academy for replication, the CSL implementation framework, behavioural intervention guidelines, and the policy recommendation package. Each result is linked to one or more SPOON partners and is currently being characterised in terms of ownership, target users, maturity, and potential exploitation route. These KERs will be further presented in this document.

The mapping of KERs is being conducted using a dedicated template and master file (maintained by PNO), which enables a structured collection of information regarding each result's description, expected use, value proposition, IP status, and alignment with exploitation channels. This information will form the basis for tailored exploitation strategies to be detailed in future deliverables (D6.2 and D6.3) and will also feed into the Communication & Dissemination activities under WP7 to leverage on the outputs value proposition.

3.1 SPOON'S KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

The preliminary list of SPOON KERs by M6 of the project is an evolution of the list presented at proposal stage and in the GA and is presented below:

Table 1. SPOON's list of preliminary KERs.

KER ID	NAME	MAIN KER OWNER
1	Expanded framework on food environment, including behavioural factors affecting European sustainable and healthy food consumption	EV-ILVO
2	Online database of best practices using CS in food system transformation	EV-ILVO
3	FAIR & GDPR compliant digital personal data wallet	JIBE
4	Multimedia questionnaire generator	JIBE
5	DataU as GDPR compliant data sharing platform	JIBE
6	Handbook for implementation and replication of CSLs and BCIs	SFC
7	Citizen Science Labs (CSLs)	INCOMMON, ITC, HBK, VIC, CITTÀ DI TORINO, BFL, Rete CdQ, MoThess
8	Guidelines for Co-Designing Behaviour Change Interventions & Intervention Data and Insights	CSCP and CSL coordinators
9	SPOON Academy for replication of CSLs	CSCP
10	Policy recommendations package	AIT
11	Citizen Science Lab monitoring toolkit	AIT
12	SWOT analysis of existing tools and platforms for sharing food data	ITC

2 TARGET GROUPS

The effective exploitation of SPOON results relies on a clear understanding of the project's TGs and their specific interests, capacities, and roles in enabling the uptake and replication of project outputs. SPOON operates within a highly multi-actor landscape, spanning from citizens and grassroots communities to municipalities, public administrations, NGOs, education providers, research organisations, and industry actors across the food value chain.

Each of these groups may engage with different types of results and through different exploitation channels. For instance, local authorities may be interested in adopting the SPOON toolset and CSLs methodologies for future participatory initiatives; while NGOs and community organisations may wish to scale specific behavioural interventions. Meanwhile, educational institutions may find value in the SPOON Academy materials and digital outputs for curricular integration, and researchers can build on SPOON's data governance frameworks or behavioural insights.

This section outlines the main categories of TGs identified in the project, their relevance to exploitation, and the envisioned strategies to reach and engage them effectively over time. The mapping presented here will be further refined in coordination with WP3 (community engagement), WP4 (CSL implementation), and WP7 (communication and dissemination) as part of the iterative exploitation strategy.

2.1 VALUE CHAIN ANALYSIS

SPOON's exploitation strategy is designed around the diversity of stakeholders involved in food system transformation. Based on their roles, capacities, and expected engagement with the project's outputs, TGs as presented in the Grant Agreement have been grouped into **four functional areas**, each with specific needs and value propositions SPOON can address and deliver.

The table below provides an overview of how each functional area and its associated TGs relate to SPOON's KERs. It summarises their specific needs and highlights which KERs are most relevant for their uptake, forming the basis for tailored exploitation strategies.

Table 2: SPOON and its contribution to the work of various stakeholders

Area	Target Group	Key Needs / Challenges	Relevant KER(s)
Area 1: Enablers and Implementers	TG2 – Municipalities, food agencies, NGOs, community leaders	Practical methodologies, planning evidence, training opportunities	3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9

	TG3 – SMEs and agri-food professionals and industries	Behavioural insights, co-creation methods, low-barrier digital engagement tools	3, 4, 5, 8
Area 2: System Shapers	TG6 – Policymakers and public authorities	Evidence-based policy, governance tools, investment/monitoring guidance	2, 10, 11, 12
	TG7 – EU-funded projects and networks	Co-production, clustering, shared tools and visibility	2, 10, 12
	TG8 – Media and influencers	Storytelling content, real-life citizen cases, reliable narratives	2, 7, 10
Area 3: Knowledge Multipliers	TG4 – Research and academic institutions	Validated methodologies, datasets, cross-sector insights	1, 2, 6, 8
	TG5 – Education and training providers	Flexible materials, video formats, behaviour change examples	7, 8, 9
Area 4: Citizen Co-Creators	TG1 – Citizens and communities in the CSLs	Empowerment, participation, food data sovereignty	3, 4, 7, 8

AREA 1: ENABLERS AND IMPLEMENTERS

Strategic approach: Local authorities, food sector professionals, and community-facing organisations play a pivotal role in translating the SPOON approach into real-world interventions. These actors are uniquely positioned to enable, adapt, and scale SPOON results through policies, services, and business models.

To support their uptake, SPOON combines tailored capacity-building (e.g. **KER9 – SPOON Academy**), scalable methodologies (**KER6 – Handbook for implementation**, **KER8 – Behaviour change guidelines**), and digital tools for engagement and data sharing (**KER3 – Personal data wallet**, **KER4 – Questionnaire generator**, **KER5 – DataU platform**). These results have been designed to be modular and transferable, offering concrete entry points for municipalities, NGOs and SMEs to build on and adapt to their local contexts.

TG 2 - MUNICIPALITIES, LOCAL/REGIONAL FOOD AGENCIES, COMMUNITY LEADERS, NGOS ACTIVE IN THE FOOD SECTOR

Municipalities and local food agencies are central to the uptake and mainstreaming of SPOON methodologies beyond the lifespan of the project. As public enablers and facilitators of community-driven change, they are in a key position to translate citizen science insights into actionable local food policies. NGOs and grassroots organisations, meanwhile, act as connectors and catalysts within communities, helping scale bottom-up initiatives. SPOON engages these actors both as co-creators in the CSLs and as long-term multipliers of its results.

Needs

- Practical methodologies to engage communities and address food insecurity.
- Evidence to support planning, implementation and evaluation of local food policies.
- Training opportunities to institutionalise citizen science approaches.

SPOON's value proposition

- The CSL framework and implementation handbook provide a replicable structure for setting up citizen-led food system actions.
- Behavioural change intervention guidelines offer tested approaches for promoting healthier, more sustainable consumption patterns.
- The SPOON Academy enables capacity-building for local officers, NGOs and community leaders seeking to mainstream these approaches.

TG3 - INDUSTRY, SMES AND PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRI-FOOD SECTOR

Food businesses and professionals are increasingly confronted with the need to integrate sustainability, transparency, and citizen engagement into their operations. From product development to marketing, from sourcing to packaging, the food sector is under pressure to respond to new consumer demands and policy frameworks. SPOON engages industry actors not only as potential users of tools and results, but also as co-creators of solutions that are rooted in community insights and behavioural evidence.

The project provides SMEs and food professionals with new opportunities to test data-driven models, leverage citizen-generated insights, and co-develop behavioural interventions that align with both sustainability goals and evolving market expectations.

Needs

- Tools to align business models with emerging consumer behaviours and expectations on data use and health.
- Access to behavioural insights and co-creation methodologies with potential customers.
- Low-barrier opportunities to test and pilot citizen-centric innovations.

SPOON's value proposition

- Insights from the CSLs help identify new behavioural patterns and market opportunities, especially around healthy and sustainable diets.
- Tools such as the **multimedia questionnaire generator**, **digital personal data wallet**, and **DataU platform** offer new ways to engage citizens and transparently manage personal data.
- Co-design approaches and practical guidelines support SMEs in embedding behavioural interventions into their services, communication, or products.

AREA 2: SYSTEM SHAPERS

Strategic approach: Policy makers and programme owners, whether operating at local, national or EU level, are key to scaling the impact of SPOON beyond its direct sphere of influence. These actors shape the regulatory and strategic environments in which innovations take root.

SPOON addresses them through policy-relevant results such as the **Policy Recommendation Package (KER10)** and the **CSL Monitoring Toolkit (KER11)**, both grounded in participatory data and tested methodologies. In parallel, synergies with fellow EU-funded initiatives are being fostered around outputs with broader transferability, such as **KER2 – Online database of best practices** and **KER12 – SWOT analysis of digital data tools**. These KERs help position SPOON within policy dialogues (e.g. FOOD2030) and support joint learning with peer projects.

In addition, SPOON will contribute to the production of six EIP-AGRI practice abstracts during the project's lifetime (in two rounds at M18 and M48), coordinated by ICONS with content input from technical partners. These abstracts will serve as concise, high-impact knowledge products tailored to agricultural stakeholders and published via the EU CAP Network. As they address themes directly linked to citizen participation, behavioural innovation and digital food data, they will reinforce the value proposition of SPOON's results, particularly for TG6 (policy actors) and TG7 (peer EU projects), while supporting clustering, visibility, and cross-project uptake.

TG6 – POLICYMAKERS AND PUBLIC AUTHORITIES

Policymakers operate across multiple levels, local, regional, national and EU, and are instrumental in shaping enabling environments for food system transformation. Their ability to mainstream successful interventions, adapt governance frameworks, and steer funding instruments makes them a priority exploitation audience for SPOON. The project builds on grounded citizen-generated evidence to deliver policy-relevant insights that are actionable, inclusive, and scalable.

Needs

- Robust, context-sensitive policy recommendations grounded in citizen participation and behavioural evidence.
- Practical tools and frameworks to support inclusive governance of local food systems.

- Insights to guide investment, regulation and monitoring in the field of sustainable nutrition.

SPOON's Value Proposition

- The **Policy Recommendations Package (KER10)** distils insights from the CSLs and the Behaviour Change Interventions, as well as the SPOON approach into targeted proposals tailored for public administrations.
- Aggregated citizen data and intervention results offer evidence for shaping future regulations and programmes on food systems.
- SPOON participation in key events, platforms (e.g., FOOD2030), and liaison with Joint Research Centre (JRC) ensures high-level visibility and alignment with EU agendas.

TG7 – FELLOW EU-FUNDED PROJECTS AND NETWORKS

Projects and networks funded under Horizon Europe, Horizon 2020 and related programmes share common objectives and often overlapping scopes with SPOON. Coordinating and aligning efforts among these initiatives enhances collective impact, avoids duplication, and fosters long-term sustainability. SPOON recognises fellow projects not only as allies in communication, but as strategic partners in joint exploitation, clustering and co-creation of knowledge.

Needs

- Opportunities for mutual visibility, knowledge sharing, and co-production of outputs.
- Common platforms to share good practices, policy messages and validated tools.
- Channels for long-term sustainability through joint replication or exploitation routes.

SPOON's Value Proposition

- Clustering activities under Task 7.4 (led by PNO) ensure regular contact and cooperation with relevant initiatives, including through the FOOD2030 platform.
- SPOON's co-organisation of multi-project events (*From SPOON to Policy* series) promotes collective outreach and impact.
- Application to Horizon Results Booster and other joint dissemination tools supports structured collaboration and shared exploitation strategies.

TG8 – MEDIA AND INFLUENCERS

Journalists, content creators, and public-facing communicators play an essential role in shaping narratives around food, health, and sustainability. They are gatekeepers of public perception and can amplify citizen voices, frame behavioural change in relatable terms, and help normalise emerging practices around data ownership and sustainable consumption. SPOON sees these actors not only as multipliers but also as creative collaborators in making the project's insights accessible and engaging for wider audiences.

Through storytelling formats such as podcasts, journalistic articles, and video content, SPOON provides rich, citizen-led material tailored to the needs of media professionals seeking inspiring, evidence-based content. This contributes directly to the project's impact goals around awareness, acceptance, and societal uptake.

Needs

- Access to credible, well-packaged content and real-life narratives that connect with public concerns about food, health and sustainability.
- Opportunities to engage with citizen stories in a way that is ethical, data-informed and visually engaging.
- Reliable data and materials to support science communication on complex topics such as food system transformation and digital sovereignty.

SPOON's Value Proposition

- SPOON produces **journalistic articles, podcast episodes, and video interviews** that feature citizens, practitioners and researchers across Europe.
- The **Best Practice Book** and CSL documentation offer compelling stories of impact and change at local level.
- Collaboration with platforms like **youris.com** (via ICONS) and media multipliers ensures visibility and outreach.
- Citizens themselves are empowered to become storytellers through co-created content formats, increasing authenticity and engagement potential.

AREA 3: KNOWLEDGE MULTIPLIERS

Strategic approach: Research institutions and educational providers are crucial for the long-term consolidation and diffusion of SPOON's approaches. By embedding citizen science methodologies and behavioural insights into academic research and learning environments, these actors ensure that SPOON's results continue to generate impact beyond the project itself.

SPOON offers reusable research assets such as the **Expanded Framework on Food Environments (KER1)**, **KER2 – Online database of CS best practices**, and methodological tools for academic exploration of behavioural and participatory interventions (**KER6, KER8**). For educators, the **SPOON Academy (KER9)** and associated materials, including tutorial videos and educational formats — provide flexible content for integration into formal and non-formal training pathways.

TG4 – RESEARCH AND ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS

Universities and research centres are vital for validating, expanding, and mainstreaming the citizen science approaches explored in SPOON. As producers of knowledge and facilitators of innovation, they benefit from access to real-world datasets, robust methodologies, and

opportunities for further exploration in the fields of food systems, behavioural science, public health, and digital governance.

Needs

- Access to validated methodologies and frameworks for citizen science in food-related research.
- Real-life datasets and evidence on behaviour change and data governance.
- Opportunities to build on SPOON results in further research and innovation projects.

SPOON's Value Proposition

- SPOON provides open datasets, behavioural insights, and tools for citizen engagement, ready to be reused or further developed.
- Methodological guidance on citizen science design and implementation supports academic work across SSH, nutrition, and ICT.
- Cross-cutting insights enable interdisciplinary research proposals aligned with the EU's FOOD2030 and Farm to Fork strategies.
- Partners involved in SPOON already contribute to research publications and are expected to continue disseminating results through peer-reviewed journals and conferences.

TG5 – EDUCATION AND TRAINING PROVIDERS

Formal and non-formal education providers, from secondary schools to adult training centres, play a pivotal role in building food literacy and empowering citizens with knowledge and skills. These actors are seeking accessible, up-to-date materials and pedagogical approaches to introduce complex food system challenges, often with limited resources or time.

SPOON responds to this need by offering modular, context-rich educational resources grounded in lived experience and co-creation.

Needs

- Practical and engaging tools to teach about food systems, sustainability, and behaviour change.
- Content that resonates with learners of different ages and backgrounds, especially through real-life examples and digital formats.
- Materials that connect theory with action and support transformative learning.

SPOON's Value Proposition

- The **SPOON Academy** offers training materials and content that can be adapted for different learning environments.
- Video tutorials, educational formats, and stories from the CSLs bring abstract concepts (e.g. food data ownership, citizen science) to life.
- SPOON's co-creative approach enables educators to engage learners not just as recipients of knowledge, but as agents of change.

AREA 4: CITIZEN CO-CREATORS

Strategic approach: Citizens are not merely end-users of SPOON outcomes, they are at the heart of its methodology, serving as co-researchers, data holders, and agents of change. The project's participatory logic empowers citizens through tools, processes, and content that are accessible, actionable, and grounded in lived experience.

Key results such as the **Digital Personal Data Wallet (KER3)** and **Multimedia Questionnaire Generator (KER4)** provide citizens with means to manage and share data on their own terms. The **Citizen Science Labs (KER7)** and co-created Behaviour Change Interventions (**KER8**) offer frameworks for participation that are inclusive and responsive to diverse needs. These results collectively reinforce citizens' roles as legitimate contributors to food system transformation.

TG1 – CITIZENS AND COMMUNITIES INVOLVED IN THE CSLS

Citizens from diverse backgrounds, including vulnerable groups disproportionately affected by food insecurity, participate in SPOON as key protagonists of knowledge creation and behavioural transformation. Their involvement is not only instrumental for data generation but is also a source of individual empowerment and collective capacity-building. Supporting their continued engagement and uptake of project results is therefore central to SPOON's exploitation vision.

Needs

- Meaningful and inclusive ways to contribute to change in the food system.
- Tools to regain agency over personal food choices and related data.
- Opportunities to build skills and continue engaging with food issues beyond the project.

SPOON's Value Proposition

- The **digital personal data wallet** (KER3) empowers citizens to manage, understand, and share their own food-related data in GDPR-compliant ways.
- The **CSL methodology** ensures inclusive and locally relevant participation processes.
- SPOON provides **behavioural interventions, informative content, and co-created tools** that are relevant, accessible and adaptable to different everyday contexts.
- Through local partners and the **Best Practice Book**, citizens' voices and stories are amplified, encouraging broader societal awareness and replication of their actions.

2.2 RELATED RESEARCH INITIATIVES

SPOON is embedded within a wider ecosystem of EU-funded projects addressing food system transformation, data governance, behavioural change, and citizen engagement. Strategic collaboration with related initiatives is essential to ensure complementarity, avoid duplication, and amplify the exploitation potential of results through clustering, joint dissemination and knowledge transfer.

As part of the ‘Target Groups’ analysis, and synergistically with the project clustering strategy of Task T7.4, SPOON has identified a series of initiatives under Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, particularly within the FOOD2030 policy framework, that offer high potential for synergies with SPOON’s outputs and TGs. These include both ongoing and recently completed projects working on adjacent domains such as citizen-centric data platforms, food environments, personalised nutrition, and digital sovereignty.

This assessment has been performed following the recommendations provided during the Kick-off Meeting by the Project Officers, as well as a desktop research analysis performed using PNO’s proprietary tool WheesBee. The desktop query performed explored projects that will be active at least during 2025 and beyond, so that there is room to further engage on joint activities.

Some key projects of strategic interest include:

- **Data4Food2030 (2022–2026)** – Developing pathways towards a fair, inclusive and innovative data economy for sustainable food systems.
- **FOODITY (2023–2025)** – Exploring respectful data innovation around food and nutrition, centred on citizen sovereignty.
- **DRG4Food (2022–2025)** – Empowering a responsible European food register through citizen involvement.
- **TITAN (2022–2026)** – Supporting transparency and traceability in food systems through digital innovation.

Few projects highlighted as references beyond the proposed criteria are:

- **FNS-Cloud (2019–2023)** – Integrating food and nutrition data across Europe to improve food system services.
- **S3FOOD, PROTEIN, and F2F Health Matters** – Providing models for sensor use, personalised nutrition, and SME-driven food innovation.

These initiatives are accessible via the FOOD2030 platform hosted by CLEVERFOOD. Moreover, internal mapping of projects with aligned KERs (e.g. dashboards, data wallets, policy recommendations, citizen science frameworks) has been developed by PNO and is being continuously updated.

Collaboration opportunities will include:

- Co-organisation of thematic policy events (e.g. *From SPOON to Policy* series).
- Joint development of dissemination formats such as infopacks and practice abstracts.
- Shared exploitation efforts through Horizon Results Booster or the FOOD2030 community.
- Cross-promotion of tools and methodologies, especially those aimed at municipalities, NGOs, and educational providers.

By building these bridges, SPOON positions its KERs within a broader landscape of impact, ensuring that its outputs are reinforced and disseminated through trusted peer networks and platforms.

The full list of projects identified (94 in total) is presented at the end of this document.

3 PRELIMINARY TRENDS ANALYSIS

This section provides a first strategic reflection on the external trends shaping the exploitation potential of SPOON's results. Rather than a static landscape review, this analysis is conceived as a **living and evolving component** of the project's exploitation approach, one that will be **iteratively updated and deepened** in the coming months as the maturity of the KERs increases and stakeholder dialogues intensify. PNO will coordinate the updates to this section, based on input gathered from project partners and ongoing policy monitoring, and reflected in future versions of the Exploitation Plan.

The trends identified here build on the original rationale presented in the SPOON Grant Agreement and have been further enriched through continuous monitoring of the European policy landscape, including developments post-2024. Together, they offer a lens through which to align SPOON's outputs with broader transformation agendas across policy, education, digital innovation and citizen participation. This forward-looking perspective will inform clustering activities, replication strategies, and targeted engagement with potential adopters and policy actors.

The following table summarises the preliminary analysis of trends and how they relate to SPOON's KERs either by promoting an enabling context for exploitation or can represent a barrier/constraint.

Table 3. Preliminary trend analysis in the context of SPOON.

Trend	Description	Enabling Context to SPOON KERs	Barriers and Constraints
1. Citizen agency and data sovereignty	A shift in EU policy from citizen consultation to co-ownership, with citizens gaining control over their personal data and how it is used. Anchored in the European Data Strategy and the recently adopted European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation (2025). References to policies or related initiatives: European Data Strategy (COM(2020)66); EHDS Regulation (COM(2022)197 final, adopted 2025).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong policy alignment with KER3 (personal data wallet), KER4 (questionnaire generator), and KER5 (DataU platform). - Supports engagement with TG2 (municipalities), TG3 (SMEs), and TG6 (policymakers). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical compliance with evolving legal frameworks may require regular updates. - Low digital literacy among some citizens could hinder adoption.
2. Behavioural insights in public policy	Increasing institutionalisation of behavioural science in EU policymaking (JRC, CCBI), with growing demand for behavioural interventions to address health, climate, and food-related challenges. References to policies or related initiatives: JRC Behavioural Insights Reports (2021–2023); CCBI Workshop Report (2024).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhances the relevance of KER6 (implementation handbook), KER7 (behavioural guidelines), and KER8 (CSL frameworks). - Facilitates uptake by TG6 (public authorities) and cross-sector application (e.g. urban planning, education). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Results must demonstrate robustness and be transferable across diverse policy contexts. - Behavioural interventions may need cultural or local adaptation.
3. Data governance for public good	Legal and strategic frameworks such as the Data Governance Act, Data Act, and EHDS promote citizen-led, transparent, and ethical data reuse. References to policies or related initiatives: Data Governance Act (Reg. EU 2022/868); Data Act (Reg. EU 2023/2854); EHDS (2025).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Validates the core design of KER3–5 (wallet, platform, generator) as GDPR-compliant and aligned with EU data reuse models. - Facilitates collaboration with TG7 (EU projects) and TG6 (data-savvy public bodies). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration with broader EU data infrastructures may pose technical or interoperability challenges. - Complexity of data governance may deter smaller stakeholders from uptake.
4. Education for systems thinking and sustainability	The GreenComp framework (JRC, 2022) promotes sustainability competencies in education, supported by new EU-level initiatives like EntreComp4Transition and the GreenComp Community. References to policies or related initiatives: GreenComp (JRC, 2022); EntreComp4Transition (2024); GreenComp Community (2024).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creates strong exploitation potential for KER9 (SPOON Academy), as well as CSL-derived content (educational formats, video tutorials). - Positions SPOON for uptake by TG5 (educators, training institutions). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SPOON materials may require localisation (languages, curricula levels).- - Institutional uptake in formal systems may depend on validation, certification or partnerships.

4 SPOON EXPLOITATION PLAN

This section presents the preliminary exploitation strategy of the SPOON project, outlining how its key results will be translated into long-term value for diverse stakeholder groups. The goal is to ensure that the project's outcomes are not only developed and validated during implementation, but also sustained, replicated, and mainstreamed beyond its formal duration.

The exploitation plan builds on the mapping of SPOON's outputs and TGs, and integrates both internal and external pathways to maximise impact. It focuses on identifying the KERs, assessing their potential for uptake, and aligning them with appropriate exploitation routes, whether commercial, non-commercial, policy-driven, or community-based.

The strategy also includes the definition of roles and responsibilities across the consortium, considerations for intellectual property rights (IPR), and the progressive refinement of exploitation pathways through internal validation activities and stakeholder engagement. This deliverable (D6.1) marks the first formal step in that process, which will be deepened and expanded through subsequent outputs (D6.2 and D6.3) over the project lifetime.

4.1 EXPLOITATION AND IPR STRATEGY

The SPOON exploitation strategy aims to ensure the long-term value and real-world uptake of the project's outcomes. It is structured as an iterative, multi-stage process that integrates stakeholder needs, partner expectations, and impact-oriented planning across the project lifecycle. The goal is to support the transformation of SPOON results, whether technical, methodological or policy-relevant, into scalable solutions and practices with lasting benefit for citizens, institutions, and the food system at large.

PNO, in close collaboration with all partners, coordinates the exploitation strategy and ensures alignment across internal assessments and external engagement activities. It is based on a structured methodology inspired by best practices in Horizon Europe, combining internal assessment tools with external engagement activities. The process builds progressively from the identification of KERs to their characterisation and validation, and ultimately to the development of tailored exploitation pathways. A summary of the twelve KERs identified so far, including their titles and ownership, is available in Table 1 (see Section "SPOON's Key Exploitable Results").

Key components of the strategy include:

1. **Identification KERs and partners' IP background and KERs** → [Ongoing – Continuous](#).

Using a dedicated master file hosted within SPOON's official repository and maintained by PNO, which collects structured information on each result:

KER ID	TRL/SRL AT PROJECT INITIATION
NAME	TRL/SRL ADVANCEMENT & JUSTIFICATION
LINKS TO PROJECT OUTPUTS	FINAL (EXPECTED) TRL/SRL
DETAILED DESCRIPTION	TARGETED SEGMENTS
MAIN KER OWNER	USE OPTIONS AND EXPLOITATION ROUTES
KER CONTRIBUTOR	PROJECT IMPACT RELEVANCE
WP	COMMENTS
EXPECTED DUE DATE	CONTACT
LEVEL OF DISSEM	

All results will also be classified depending on its typology, which will help the in-depth exploitation planning and core messages definition towards the project TGs.

2. **KERs' maturity assessment** → **Continuation of characterisation activities**

The next step involves assessing the technological or societal maturity of each KER, through internal consultations, partner feedback, and the use of the **Innovation Radar** framework. This will help identify the most promising results for prioritisation and deeper exploitation efforts. Results will be mapped along TRL/SRL dimensions and readiness for uptake by TGs.

3. **KER detailed exploitation plans** → **Continuation of characterisation activities**

Selected KERs will undergo more detailed exploitation planning.

4. **Identification and characterisation of IP Foreground** → **Continuation of characterisation activities**

All foreground generated will follow Horizon Europe rules for IPR and the provisions of the Consortium Agreement.

4.2 NEXT STEPS – PATHWAY TO EXPLOITATION

PROPOSED PATHWAY TO EXPLOITATION

The diagram below illustrates SPOON's preliminary pathway to exploitation. Starting from the early identification and structured characterisation of KERs, the process advances through a first maturity assessment and leads to the definition of preliminary exploitation options and IPR strategies. Deliverable D6.1 (M6) represents the first formal milestone in this trajectory, consolidating the work done so far and laying the foundation for the next steps planned between M12 and M18. This approach ensures an iterative and evidence-based progression from knowledge creation to result uptake.

Figure 1. Proposed pathway to exploitation M1-M18.

MATURITY ASSESSMENT OF KERS

To support a structured and evidence-based exploitation strategy, SPOON adopts a maturity assessment methodology developed by PNO and inspired by the European Commission’s **Innovation Radar**. This methodology evaluates each KER not only in terms of its technical advancement but also based on its potential for innovation uptake and real-world impact. The assessment is carried out in two dimensions (presented in Figure 2 below): the **Innovation Potential Indicator** and the **Innovator Capacity Indicator**, each composed of sub-criteria that provide a detailed view of strengths and areas for development.

The **Innovation Potential Indicator** focuses on market relevance, innovation readiness, and result management within the project. It helps determine how close a result is to reaching a context of application or transfer. The **Innovator Capacity Indicator**, on the other hand, assesses the ability and commitment of the partners owning or developing each KER to bring it to market or societal uptake. This includes their environment, expertise, and strategic orientation. The combination of these two perspectives allows SPOON to prioritise its efforts on the most promising results and to tailor exploitation routes according to the maturity and ambition of each result-owner.

Figure 2. The diagrams of the Innovation Radar methodology.

DETAILED CHARACTERISATION OF KERS

For each KER, different aspects will be considered when relevant. The table presented below includes all the elements that will be considered for each individual exploitation plan, delivered at the end of the project for the KERs with higher results (obtained through a maturity ranking) at the final stages of the IP and Exploitation Strategy.

The Novel Solution - Product & Problem	
Description of the Result	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e. product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your USP is delivered</i>
Problems you are addressing and how your customers solve them so far	<i>Problems you are addressing and how your customers solve them so far. What are the user's gains? What are their gains from your solution?</i>
Market - Customers & Competitors	
Market Trends	<i>What are the market trends related to your solution? It should include quantitative data.</i>
"Market" – Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments? To finalise the exploitation plan and prepare the use of the KER a clear identification of the target market is needed, with its segmentation. Please consider that geography matters in terms of the market that you want to serve.</i>
Product/Service Positioning	<i>Product positioning is a marketing technique intended to present products in the best possible light to different Target Groups (customers).</i>
Product/Service Market Size	<i>Market size is the number of individuals in a certain market segment who are potential buyers. To calculate your market size, you'll either be looking for data on the number of potential customers, or number of transactions each year. Describe the segment on the market in which your product/service can compete.</i>

Early Adopters - First Customers	<i>Typically, this will be a customer who, in addition to using the vendor's product or technology, will also provide considerable and candid feedback to help the vendor refine its future product releases, as well as the associated means of distribution, service, and support. Early adoption could also be referred to as a form of testing in the early stages of a project.</i>
Competitors/Incumbents	<i>The term incumbent is used to refer to a leader company with a large market share. Who are the competitors?</i>
Unique Selling Point	<i>A unique selling proposition (USP, also seen as unique selling point) is a factor that differentiates a product from its competitors, such as the lowest cost, the highest quality or the first-ever product of its kind. A USP could be thought of as “what you have that competitors don’t.” Describe how your product/service differs from competitors, competitive advantage.</i>
Legal or normative or ethical requirements & public acceptance	
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	<i>Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorizations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.). Are there any critical ethical, privacy, safety or security issues? Do you address all relevant regulatory aspects or standards/norms?</i>
Public Acceptance	<i>Public acceptance should be considered as a key commercial challenge.</i>
Exploitation strategy - Activities, Costs, Financing	
Time to market (from the end of the project)	<i>Time to market (TTM) is the length of time it takes from a product being conceived until its being available for sale. Indicate expected time for the KER to reach the market from the end of the project.</i>
Adequateness of Consortium Staff	<i>Adequateness of Consortium Staff. Availability of the right skills, number of human resources needed, missing skills.</i>
Cost of implementation - bringing product/service to the “market” (before Exploitation)	<i>Cost of implementation - bringing product/service to the “market” (before Exploitation).</i>
Sources of financing foreseen after the end of the project	<i>Venture capital, loans, other European, national, regional grants, own financing, collaborative agreements.</i>
Foreseen Product/Service Price	<i>Foreseen Product/Service Price.</i>

Intellectual Property Rights	
Status of IPR: Background (type and partner owner)	<i>Indicate relevant knowledge/IP supplied at the start of the project.</i>
Status of IPR: Results/Foreground (type and partner owner)	<i>Indicate relevant knowledge/IP produced during the project.</i>
Status of IPR: use the results from the Exploitation Form	<i>Indicate relevant knowledge/IP produced by partners outside the project during/after the project tenure.</i>
Partner/s involved expectations	<i>What are the exploitation interests of the project partners?</i>
Initial TRL/SRL	<i>TRL/SRL of the KER before SPOON</i>
Final TRL/SRL	<i>Expected TRL/SRL of the KER after SPOON</i>

5 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable D6.1 sets the foundation for the SPOON exploitation strategy by consolidating the preliminary list of KERs, framing the project's engagement with key TGs, and outlining the tools and processes that will support exploitation activities throughout the project lifecycle. Rather than offering definitive exploitation plans, this first version provides a shared structure and strategic direction for their progressive development.

Through its mapping of stakeholders, alignment with emerging European trends, and integration of internal mechanisms such as the KER master file and maturity assessment framework, this deliverable ensures that exploitation in SPOON is treated as a continuous, structured, and impact-oriented process. It also reinforces the project's connection to the broader FOOD2030 agenda and the EU's evolving priorities around citizen participation, behavioural innovation, and ethical data governance.

Subsequent deliverables (D6.2 and D6.3) will build on this initial framework, integrating updated characterisations of the KERs, partner-driven exploitation intentions, and feedback from stakeholder engagement activities. These next steps will allow the consortium to define more specific exploitation pathways, identify potential early adopters, and explore opportunities for replication, scale-up and policy uptake. As such, this deliverable should be understood as the starting point of a dynamic, iterative process, one that evolves alongside the project's results and stakeholder ecosystem.

ANNEX – LIST OF IDENTIFIED PROJECTS

Project Id	Acronym	Title	Start Date	End Date
CORDIS-266880	SPOON	Food Systems in transition – Participatory, Open citizen research for sustainable Nutrition	01/12/2024	30/11/2028
CORDIS-241992	FEAST	FEAST	01/07/2022	30/06/2027
CORDIS-241136	FOODCLIC	integrated urban FOOD policies – developing sustainability Co-benefits, spatial Linkages, social Inclusion and sectoral Connections to transform food systems in city-regions	01/09/2022	28/02/2027
CORDIS-266353	FOODMISSION	Engaging citizens as agents of change for sustainable food system transition with a novel gamified educational citizen science platform	01/01/2025	30/06/2028
CORDIS-241887	PLANEAT	Food systems transformation towards healthy and sustainable dietary behaviour	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-240094	REACT	Rapid elimination of invasive insect agricultural pest outbreaks by tackling them with Sterile Insect Technique programs	01/11/2022	31/10/2026
CORDIS-242462	LIKE-A-PRO	From niche to mainstream - alternative proteins for everybody and everywhere	01/11/2022	31/10/2026
CORDIS-238760	GES4SEAS	Achieving Good Environmental Status for maintaining ecosystem Services, by Assessing integrated impacts of cumulative pressures	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-265908	DOMESTIC	The role of domestic markets and public policy for sustainable food systems: the case of Brazil	01/01/2025	31/12/2029
CORDIS-241783	Impetus	Impetus	01/07/2022	30/06/2026
CORDIS-267086	DietWise	DietWise: Systemic Solutions to Enhance Healthy and Sustainable Food Provision and Cooking at Home	01/11/2024	31/10/2027
CORDIS-241251	BIONEXT	The Biodiversity Nexus: transformative change for sustainability	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-241947	TITAN	Transparency solutions for transforming the food system.	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-238626	IDAlert	Infectious Disease decision-support tools and Alert systems to build climate Resilience to emerging health Threats	01/06/2022	31/05/2027
CORDIS-233506	PHIL_OS	A Philosophy of Open Science for Diverse Research Environments	01/09/2021	31/08/2026
CORDIS-241336	ECS	European Citizen Science	01/08/2022	31/07/2026
CORDIS-244692	BioLaMer	Proof of principle fly larvae biorefinery for biopolymer plastic production	01/04/2023	31/03/2026
CORDIS-241474	ETAİN	Exposure To electromAgnetic fields and plaNetary health	01/06/2022	31/05/2027
CORDIS-243777	GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation (societal and cultural domains)	01/02/2023	31/01/2026
CORDIS-237197	EPND	European platform for neurodegenerative disorders	01/11/2021	31/10/2026
CORDIS-241271	OEMC	Open-Earth-Monitor Cyberinfrastructure	01/06/2022	31/05/2026
CORDIS-237034	SISTERS	Systemic Innovations for a SusTainable reduction of the EuRopean food waStage	01/11/2021	30/04/2026
CORDIS-236567	MINAGRIS	Micro- and Nano-Plastics in AGRicultural Soils: sources, environmental fate and impacts on ecosystem services and overall sustainability	01/09/2021	31/08/2026
CORDIS-240388	TRIGGER	SoluTions foR mltiGatinG climate-induced hEalth tReaths	01/09/2022	28/02/2027
CORDIS-236264	Arctic PASSION	Pan-Arctic observing System of Systems: Implementing Observations for societal Needs	01/07/2021	31/12/2025
CORDIS-241936	RICH Europe	Research Infrastructures Consortium of NCPs in Horizon Europe	01/06/2022	31/05/2029
CORDIS-244162	PATTERN	Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks	01/01/2023	30/06/2026
CORDIS-241194	BEPREP	Identification of best practices for biodiversity recovery and public health interventions to prevent future epidemics and pandemics	01/09/2022	28/02/2027

CORDIS-241244	ToNoWaste	TOWARDS A NEW ZERO FOOD WASTE MINDSET BASED ON HOLISTIC ASSESSMENT	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-253112	Strategic Synergies	Strategic Synergies Cluster XKIC BP 23-25 Proposal	01/01/2023	31/12/2025
CORDIS-260714	FNIT	Comprehensive Framework for the Future of Water-Energy-Food Nexus and Socio-Environmental Issues in a Transboundary River Basin (FNIT)	01/07/2024	30/06/2026
CORDIS-241825	RURALITIES	Climate smart, ecosystem-enhancing and knowledge-based rural expertise and training centres	01/10/2022	30/09/2027
CORDIS-241943	BEATLES	Co-creating Behavioural Change Towards Climate-Smart Food Systems	01/07/2022	30/06/2026
CORDIS-258081	TRACES	Tracking Long-Term Resilience in Arctic Sociocultural-Ecological Systems	01/01/2024	31/12/2028
CORDIS-243512	BEYOND	Beyond Bad Apples: Towards a Behavioral and Evidence-Based Approach to Promote Research Ethics and Research Integrity in Europe	01/01/2023	31/12/2025
CORDIS-243029	NBSoil	Nature Based Solutions for Soil Management	01/12/2022	30/11/2026
CORDIS-237090	WaterLANDS	Water-based solutions for carbon storage, people and wilderness	01/12/2021	30/11/2026
CORDIS-264718	ArcSolution	Arctic Pollution in a One Health perspective - from complex challenges to sustainable solutions	01/08/2024	31/07/2028
CORDIS-254283	BOSTAN TREE	Bioarchaeology of Orchards and Sustainable Terroir in the Arid Near East – Trends in Ecology and Evolution	01/01/2024	31/12/2028
CORDIS-241536	WET HORIZONS	WET HORIZONS - upgrading knowledge and solutions to fast-track wetland restoration across Europe	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-242762	PIANOFORTE	Partnership for european research in radiation protection and detection of ionising radiation : towards a safer use and improved protection of the environment and human health.	01/06/2022	31/05/2027
CORDIS-240414	MAMBO	Modern Approaches to the Monitoring of Biodiversity	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-243503	aUPaEU	A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities	01/01/2023	31/12/2027
CORDIS-242291	OBAMA-NEXT	OBSERVING AND MAPPING MARINE ECOSYSTEMS – NEXT GENERATION TOOLS	01/12/2022	30/11/2026
CORDIS-241741	NEVERMORE	New Enabling Visions and tools for End-users and stakeholders thanks to a common MOdeling fRamework towards a climatE neutral and resilient society	01/06/2022	31/05/2026
CORDIS-237028	REFLECT AFRICA	RENEWABLE ENERGIES FOR AFRICA: EFFECTIVE VALORIZATION OF AGRI-FOOD WASTES	01/11/2021	31/10/2026
CORDIS-240101	RUSTIK	Rural Sustainability Transitions through Integration of Knowledge for improved policy processes	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-237095	SHARED GREEN DEAL	SHARED GREEN DEAL: Social sciences & Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable GREEN DEAL	01/02/2022	31/01/2027
CORDIS-242285	MAR2PROTECT	PREVENTING GROUNDWATER CONTAMINATION RELATED TO GLOBAL AND CLIMATE CHANGE THROUGH A HOLISTIC APPROACH ON MANAGED AQUIFER RECHARGE	01/12/2022	30/11/2026
CORDIS-243339	R4C	Regions4Climate	01/01/2023	31/12/2027
CORDIS-241164	Biodiversa-plus	The European Biodiversity Partnership	01/10/2021	30/09/2028
CORDIS-241838	GRANULAR	Giving Rural Actors Novel data and re-Useable tools to Lead public Action in Rural areas	01/10/2022	30/09/2026
CORDIS-240907	The HuT	The Human-Tech Nexus - Building a Safe Haven to cope with Climate Extremes	01/10/2022	30/09/2026
CORDIS-242638	SDGs-EYES	Sustainable Development Goals - Enhanced monitoring through the family of copernicus Services	01/01/2023	31/12/2025
CORDIS-241210	LAMASUS	Land use and Management modelling for Sustainable governance	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-241489	MAGICA	Maximising the synergy of European research Governance and Innovation for Climate Action	01/06/2022	31/05/2026
CORDIS-242034	DIRECTED	Disaster Resilience for Extreme Climate Events providing interoperable Data, models, communication and governance	01/10/2022	30/09/2026
CORDIS-241256	ENFASYS	Encouraging Farmers towards sustainable farming Systems through policy and business Strategies	01/09/2022	31/08/2026

CORDIS-242521	FLIARA	FLIARA: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas	01/01/2023	31/12/2025
CORDIS-237063	ECF4CLIM	A EUROPEAN COMPETENCE FRAMEWORK FOR A LOW CARBON ECONOMY AND SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH EDUCATION	01/10/2021	31/12/2025
CORDIS-238636	K-HEALTHinAIR	Knowledge for improving indoor AIR quality and HEALTH	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-243308	BENCHMARKS	Building a European Network for the Characterisation and Harmonisation of Monitoring Approaches for Research and Knowledge on Soils	01/01/2023	31/12/2027
CORDIS-235774	FUTUREROADS	Future Roads Fellowships	01/10/2021	30/09/2026
CORDIS-238880	SynAir-G	Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing, using Advanced Intelligent Multisensing and Green Interventions	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-238594	PathFinder	Towards an Integrated Consistent European LULUCF Monitoring and Policy Pathway Assessment Framework.	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-259128	GreenInCities	GreenInCities	01/01/2024	31/12/2027
CORDIS-243929	REINFORCING	Responsible tErritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance	01/01/2023	28/02/2027
CORDIS-244313	EcoDaLLi	ECOSystem-based governance with DANube lighthouse Living Lab for sustainable Innovation processes	01/01/2023	30/06/2026
CORDIS-242410	KITE	Kiel Training for Excellence	01/01/2023	31/12/2027
CORDIS-237919	SSH CENTRE	Social Sciences and Humanities for Climate, Energy aNd Transport Research Excellence	01/09/2022	28/02/2026
CORDIS-241779	Cardea	CARDEA - Career Acknowledgement for Research (Managers) Delivering for the European Area	01/06/2022	31/05/2026
CORDIS-241216	SYMBIOREM	Symbiotic, circular bioremediation systems and biotechnology solutions for improved environmental, economic and social sustainability in pollution control	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-242156	POLICY ANSWERS	R&I POLICY making, implementation ANd Support in the WEsteRn BalkanS	01/03/2022	28/02/2026
CORDIS-243763	SOLARIS	Strengthening demOcratic engagement through vaLue-bAsed geneRative adversarial networkS	01/02/2023	31/01/2026
CORDIS-242196	SEED	Systems and Engineering Science Doctorate	01/09/2023	31/08/2028
CORDIS-238754	B-THENET	BEST PRACTICES AND INNOVATIONS FOR A SUSTAINABLE BEEKEEPING	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-237094	PROBONO	The Integrator-centric approach for realising innovative energy efficient buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods	01/01/2022	31/12/2026
CORDIS-242250	CULTUURCAMPUS	Cultuurcampus: a sustainable hub of arts, research, learning and community as catalyst	01/10/2022	31/12/2025
CORDIS-238744	Marine SABRES	Marine Systems Approaches for Biodiversity Resilience and Ecosystem Sustainability	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-243444	DANUBE4all	RESTORATION OF THE DANUBE RIVER BASIN WATERS FOR ECOSYSTEMS AND PEOPLE FROM MOUNTAINS TO COAST	01/01/2023	31/12/2027
CORDIS-236475	JUSTNature	Activation of NATURE-based solutions for a JUST low carbon transition	01/09/2021	28/02/2026
CORDIS-241449	NextGEM	Next Generation Integrated Sensing and Analytical System for Monitoring and Assessing Radiofrequency Electromagnetic Field Exposure and Health	01/07/2022	30/06/2026
CORDIS-241208	NaturaConnect	NaturaConnect - Designing a resilient and coherent Trans-European Network for Nature and People	01/07/2022	30/06/2026
CORDIS-242980	BCThubs	Blue Culture Technology Excellence Hubs in EU Widening Member States	01/01/2023	31/12/2026
CORDIS-229827	EUTOPIA-SIF	EUTOPIA-Science and Innovation Fellowships	01/05/2021	31/10/2026
CORDIS-243917	Accelerate_FutureHEI	Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Acceleration Programme	01/01/2023	31/12/2026
CORDIS-238645	TwinAIR	Digital Twins Enabled Indoor Air Quality Management for Healthy Living	01/09/2022	31/08/2026
CORDIS-239021	D4RUNOFF	Data driven implementation of hybrid nature based solutions for preventing and managing diffuse pollution from urban water runoff	01/09/2022	28/02/2026
CORDIS-237114	REST-COAST	Large scale RESToration of COASTal ecosystems through rivers to sea connectivity	01/10/2021	31/03/2026

CORDIS-243044	METACITIES	MetaCities Excellence Hub in South-Eastern Europe	01/01/2023	31/12/2026
CORDIS-244206	EDCTP Africa Office	Strengthening global cooperation and institutional capacities in sub-Saharan Africa to facilitate implementation of the GH EDCTP3 programme	01/01/2023	31/12/2025
CORDIS-243790	RESIST	Regions for climate change resilience through Innovation, Science and Technology	01/01/2023	31/12/2027
CORDIS-243287	SLEs	STE(A)M Learning Ecologies	01/01/2023	31/12/2025
CORDIS-243767	Tracks4Crafts	Transforming crafts knowledge for a sustainable, inclusive and economically viable heritage in Europe	01/03/2023	28/02/2027

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